

PROCEDURAL JUSTICE, JOB AUTONOMY, AND ORGANIZATIONAL CITIZENSHIP BEHAVIOUR AMONG NURSES

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Abstract

The primary objective of this research was to examine the influence of procedural justice, job Autonomy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior among nurses. Its purpose was to determine the association between Procedural Justice (PJ), job autonomy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior among nurses from various public and private sectors. Based on previous literature, following hypothesis were formulated: 1) there would be a significant negative

relationship between procedural justice and job autonomy. 2) There would be a significant negative relationship between job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior. 3) There would be significant positive relationship between Procedural Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. 4) Public hospital nurses would have high levels of job autonomy as compare to private hospital sector nurses. The convenient sample consisted of 260 nurses from age range of 18 years to 60 years working in private and public hospitals in urban and rural areas of Sialkot. A questionnaire comprised of self-developed demographic sheet with scales of Measurement of distributive and procedural justice (Lucas, 2007), Job autonomy scale (Fida & Najam, 2019) and Organizational

Citizenship Behavior Checklist short form (Spector, 2010). Descriptive statistics, Cronbach's alpha, Pearson product moment correlation, one way ANOVA and independent sample t-test were computed. The findings suggested that procedural justice has a significantly weak negative correlation with job autonomy ($r=-.15$, $p<.05$) and a significantly moderate positive correlation with organizational citizenship behavior ($r= .484$, $p< .001$). Pearson's product of job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior was found to be weak negative and statistically significant ($r=-.273$, $p<.001$). One way ANOVA results showed that diploma-holder nurses have a higher level of job autonomy as compared to any other education programs. Independent sample t-test was used to examine the private and public sectors difference showing a significant difference in private sector healthcare professionals ($M=70.51$, $SD= 10.89$) and the government sector healthcare professionals ($M=74.08$, $SD=12.89$), $t(3.32)$, $p < .01$. The study highlighted the significance of fairness of procedures and approaches in the hospitals aided the nurses in the performance of assigned responsibilities independently, therefore resulting in the organization's successful and efficient operation.

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of the survey conducted by the World Health Organization (WHO) depicted that accomplishing the purpose of promoting health and enhancing well-being requires nine million nurses by 2030 globally (Harahsheh et al., 2020). The nurses have a remarkable role in influencing the results of the patient's condition and the general quality of health and well-being by being the frontline workers (Ibrahim & Abdelrahim, 2023).

Healthcare nurses employed in particular hospital sectors are subjected to perform activities that are auxiliary and additional and are not the demand of their assigned role duties if they perceive a high degree of justice and equity in their organizations (Lönnqvist et al., 2022; Dong & Lu, 2020). Procedural justice demonstrated a stronger correlation with organizational loyalty and trust in upper management. (Folger & Konovsky, 1998)

Work autonomy is the extent to which a person has a great deal of flexibility in their area of work, including the ability to plan their work and determine how best to do their tasks (Morgeson & Ojeleye, 2022). The “Taylor style” is a conventional management paradigm that proposes that the organization creates hindrances to the worker’s duty. One of the essential causes for decreasing workers’ eagerness and inhibiting innovation is confined job autonomy. Workers' inspiration and novelty are upgraded by gradually executing job autonomy strategies in the organizations. Morgeson and Humphrey conducted a study that unveiled that when employees are confronted with trivial job autonomy, tiresome duty, and insufficient expertise are the factors of declining employee efficiency. Therefore, workers acquiring greater job autonomy probably engaged in greater organizational citizenship behaviors (Zhou, 2020).

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is significantly influenced by job autonomy. Increased OCB from job autonomy can benefit firms in the form of enhanced performance, happier workers, and a supportive and proactive culture (Hwang & Sim, 2022). Jehanzeb et al. (2020) elaborated that organizational citizenship behaviors (OCB) can be described as the actions performed by the employees of an organization that is voluntary and additional and the organization is not responsible for the compensation of the employees for their voluntary participation informally. Stable relationships and interpersonal citizenship behavior share an affirmative association, on the other hand, if the relationships in the organization weaken then the pessimism established from it can minimize interpersonal citizenship behavior (Lee, 2022).

Latif & Pamikatsih (2020) elaborated that Procedural Justice (PJ) shares an affirmative association with Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB). The notion of Procedural Justice (PJ) in workers promotes the sense of worth as a fundamental component of the organization, eventually resulting in the enhanced OCB in the organization.

Objectives of Study

The study aims:

1. To determine the association between Procedural Justice (PJ), job autonomy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).
2. To explore the difference in the Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) of private and public hospitals.
3. To evaluate that the fairness of procedures and approaches in the hospitals aids the nurses in the performance of assigned responsibilities independently, therefore resulting in the organization's successful and efficient operation.
4. To determine how the influence of procedural justice upon organizational citizenship behaviour on nurses, may play a crucial and vital role in the effective functioning of hospitals.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The cross-sectional research design was used in this research.

Participants

A purposive sample of 260 consisted nurses (N= 126 from private hospitals, N = 134 from public hospitals) from various healthcare centers. The sample comprised nurses within an age range of 18 years to 60 years working in private and public hospitals in urban and rural areas. Nurses having minimum experience of less than a year to a maximum number of years of clinical years' experience such as more than 10 years of practice were included. Both male and female nurses belonging to any religion were included. Nurses less than 18 years old and above 60 years were excluded.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

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Measures

Three standardized instruments were administered:

1. **Measurement of Distributive Justice and Procedural for Self and Others (MPDJ): Lucas et al., 2007):** The Scale of Distributive Justice and Procedural Justice Belief for Self and Others (Lucas, 2007) comprised 21 items rated on a 7-point Likert scale. Higher scores indicate stronger belief in justice for self and others.
2. **Job Autonomy Scale (Fida & Najam, 2019):** The Job Autonomy Scale (Fida & Najam, 2019) initially consists of Forty-four items to measure job autonomy. After factor analysis, the number of items was reduced to 28 on a 5- point Likert scale. Higher scores indicate greater job autonomy.
3. **Organizational Citizenship Behavior- Checklist (OCB-C Short Form: Spector et al., 2010):** The Organizational Citizenship Behavior Checklist (Spector, 2010) is a 10-item scale that measures the frequency of civic behaviors in the workplace on a 5-point Likert scale. Higher scores indicate greater civic behavior among nurses.

All instruments demonstrated acceptable reliability in this study.

Procedure

At first, the synopsis of the study was accepted by the Department Research Committee (DRC) of the Department of Psychology, GC Woman University, Sialkot. Subsequently, permission was obtained from university officials to conduct a thesis for research and data collection through simple questionnaires from the hospital sectors. The permission for the utilization of scales from their respective authors was secured formerly conducting the research. . Further, officials from various

hospitals were requested for permission to collect data from their respective staff working in various departments. Then, participants located in Sialkot City of Pakistan were provided questionnaires consisting of a letter of consent along with a demographic sheet and scales of the current study i.e.; Measurement of Procedural and Distributive Justice for Self and Others (MPDJ: Lucas et al., 2007), Job Autonomy Scale (Fida & Najam, 2019), and Organizational Citizenship Behavior- Checklist (OCB-C Short Form: Spector et al., 2010) were filled out. Participants were informed that their responses would be kept confidential. A total sample of 260 nurses from private and public sectors aged 18 years to 60 years was selected using a purposive sampling technique. For data analysis, descriptive analysis and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient, One-way ANOVA and independent sample t -test was employed using statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, 27) to examine relationship between variables. The ethical guidelines were prioritized during the whole procedure of research. Participants were debriefed about the study findings.

RESULTS

To interpret the data descriptive statistics, the Pearson product coefficient correlation method, independent sample t -test, and one-way ANOVA methods were applied through the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS, 27).

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of the Procedural Justice, Job Autonomy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior among Nurses (Frequencies & Percentages)

Variables	<i>F</i>	%
Age		
18-28	135	51.9
29-38	64	24.6
39-48	41	15.8

Razzaq et al - 2026

3007-2387

3007-2379

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49-58	20	7.7
Religion		
Islam	160	61.5
Christian	100	38.5
Living Area		
Rural	111	42.7
Urban	149	57.3
Socio-economic Status		
Lower Class	18	6.9
Middle Class	227	87.3
Upper Class	15	5.8
Education		
Diploma	146	56.2
BSN	101	38.8
Any other	13	5.0
Hospital Sector		
Private	126	48.5
Government	134	51.5
Ward		
Emergency Ward	125	48.1
General Ward	135	51.9
Designation		
Internees	72	27.7
Charge Nurse	123	47.3
Head Nurse	23	8.8
Superintendent	10	3.8

Razzaq et al - 2026

3007-2387

3007-2379

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Any Other	32	12.3
Monthly Income		
Zero	14	5.4
1 to 30,000	80	30.8
30,000-60.000	117	45.0
60,000-90,000	34	13.1
More than 90,000	15	5.8
Experience		
Less than 1 year	71	27.3
1-3 year	46	17.7
3-6 year	41	15.8
6-9 year	29	11.2
More than 9 years	73	28.1
Working Hours		
4-8 Hours	192	73.8
8-12 Hours	55	21.2
More than 12 Hours	13	5.0
	<i>F</i>	%
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Working Hours		
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More than 12 Hours	13	5.0

Sample Description

The table shows the demographic data for the participants. 260 sample representing 51.9% of nurses who were in the age group of 18-28 years, 24.5% of nurses from the 28-38 years age group, 15.8% of nurses were from 39-48 years age group and 7.7% nurses were from 49-58 years age group. 61.5% of nurses were Muslim and 38.5% nurses are Christian. 42.7% nurses were belonging to rural areas and 57.3% of nurses belong to urban areas. 6.9% of nurses were from the lower class, 87.3% of nurses were from the middle class 5.8% of nurses were from upper class socioeconomic status. 56.2% of nurses had done diploma, 38.8% of nurses completed their BSN, and 5.0% nurse who had completed other degree. 260 sample representing 48.5% nurse work in private sector and 51.5% nurse's work in government sector. 48.1% of nurses work in the emergency ward and 51.9% nurses work in the general ward. 27.7% of nurses are interneers, 47.3% of nurses are charge nurses,

8.8% of nurses are head nurses, 3.8% of nurses are superintendents and 12.3% of nurses belong to other designations. 5.4% of nurses had no monthly income, 30.8% of nurses had 1-30,000 monthly income, 45.0% of nurses have 30,000-60.000 monthly income, 13.1% of nurses had 60,000-90,000 monthly income and 5.8% nurses has more than 90,000 monthly incomes. 27.3% of nurses had experience of less than 1 year, 17.7% of nurses had 1-3 years' experience, 15.8% of nurses had 3-6 years' experience, 11.2% of nurses had 6- year experience, and 28.1% of nurses had more than 9- year experience. 73.8% of nurses were serving for 4-8 hours, 21.2% of nurses were serving for 8-12 hours and 5.0% of nurses' duty timing was 12 hours.

Table 2

Correlation between Procedural Justice, Job Autonomy and Organizational Citizenship Behavior among Nurses (N=260)

Variables	1	2	3
1. Procedural Justice	–		
2. Job Autonomy	-.15*	–	
3. Organizational Citizenship Behavior	.484**	-.273**	–

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .001$

According to the table 2, the following correlation exists between Procedural justice, job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior $-.15^*$, $-.273^{**}$ and $.484^{**}$ which were all significant. The findings revealed that there was a statistically significant relationship between three variables

Table 3

Mean, standard deviation, and one-way ANOVA of procedural justice, job autonomy, and organizational citizenship behavior

Variables	Diploma		BSN		Any Other		F	P
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
MPD	36.17	8.21	37.45	6.50	35.15	8.10	1.10	.001
FNJA	68.94	10.90	76.67	12.19	77.00	12.15	14.6	
OCB	38.03	6.97	38.82	4.71	38.00	7.26	.499	

Table 3 shows that diploma-holder nurses have a higher level of job autonomy as compared to any other education programs. Overall results shows that the value of p is (.00 which is <than p) that's less than .05 which means is a significant statistical relationship among three variables regarding education.

Table 4

Mean, SD and T-Test of Private and Government Hospital Sector on FNJAS

Variables		M	SD	t(260)	P	Cohen's d
FNJAS total						
Hospital sector	Private sector	70.51	10.89	3.32	0.01	0.30
	Govt. sector	74.08	12.89			

Table 4 shows that the mean comparison and SD values indicate there was a greater difference in the level of FNJAS i.e., for the private sector (M=70.51, SD= 10.89) and in the government sector (M=74.08, SD=12.89). The p-value was 0.01 which was less than 0.05 which verified that there was significant difference exists between two variables.

DISCUSSION

This study examined the association between procedural justice, job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior among nurses emphasizing their significance in fostering the effectiveness and efficient functioning of the organization.

According to our formulated hypothesis 1 “there would be a significant negative relationship between procedural justice and job autonomy” Our findings reveal that there is a significant negative association between procedural justice and job autonomy among nurses. This suggests that the employee's perception of fairness in the organizational procedures and strategies leads to a decreased experience of freedom and independence in their job-related tasks. Our findings are consistent with the Lisanne and Marius research which suggested that the connection between distributive justice and procedural justice is most likely to expect the well-being outcomes in employees perceiving negative levels of autonomy.

According to our formulated hypothesis 2 “there would be a significant negative relationship between job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior” Our findings reveal that there is significant negative relationship between job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) among nurses. This suggests that as nurses are given more autonomy in their work, they are less likely to engage in extra-role behaviors that benefit the organization. This finding is supported by research that suggests excessive autonomy can lead to decreased accountability and a sense of disconnection from the organization (Morgeson et al., 2010).

According to the third hypothesis, “there would be a significant positive relationship between Procedural Justice and Organizational Citizenship Behavior” and findings highlighted that, Procedural justice has significant positive correlation with organizational citizenship behavior (as mentioned in table 2). The reason behind this is quite evident that, nurses feel organizational policies and procedures are free from bias and fair when they experience procedural justice. (Shehzadi & Akhter, 2024) They are more willing to engage in OCB, such as offering support to coworkers or volunteering for extra work, when they receive respect and dignity from the

organization. If workers think that their boss or organization has shown or will show fairness in the resource allocation processes, they will repay the social incentive in the form of OCBs (Pillai et al., 1999).

According to the fourth hypothesis, “Public hospital nurses would have high levels of job autonomy as compared to private hospital sector nurses.” findings highlighted that significant Job autonomy is higher in public sector hospitals than private hospitals. (As mentioned in table 4). The reason behind this is quite evident that nurses feel free to control procedures and policies in government hospitals rather than in private hospitals. Public hospital regulations and procedures are like those that spend less time for nurses and all staff members in making choices with high authority or waiting for other orders (Khalid & Akhtar, 2025) additionally, this can support nurses in making choices that enhance their performance as a whole including job autonomy. Contrarily, there’s less job autonomy at private hospitals. The results of job autonomy are modeled by using transformational leadership theory. This theory gives importance to leaders' inspiration and motivation which they give to their employees to accomplish shared objectives or goals. It is well known that transformational leaders provide their followers freedom and autonomy in the workplace. According to Avolio et al. (1999), transformational leadership can boost followers’ sense of agency, autonomy, and empowerment, which can improve their output work satisfaction, and OCB.

CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS

The present study explores the relationship of procedural justice, job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior among nurses. There’s negative relationship among PJ and Job autonomy which means that employees tend to have more autonomy at work when they perceive unfair procedures and decision-making processes (low procedural justice) and also significant negative relationship among Job autonomy and OCB which means as JA increases, OCB decreases. Positive correlation among PJ and OCB suggests that as employees perceive fair procedures in an organization, they tend to have more organizational citizenship behavior (high OCB). Other than PJ and OCB, the Job

Autonomy is higher in public hospitals as compared to private hospital. One way ANOVA analysis revealed that diploma-holder nurses have a higher level of job autonomy as compared to any other education programs. Additionally, T-test results revealed a substantial impact of job autonomy differences between public healthcare sectors and private healthcare sectors.

LIMITATION AND RECOMMENDATION

This study is limited because data is collected only from the nurses of specific regions which may limit the applicability of research findings. The majority of nurses were preoccupied with tending to patients, therefore there would be social desirability or biased responses. There were more females in the data than males, making it impossible to examine gender differences. Furthermore, the results cannot be applied to both genders because there were fewer male participants. Future research may replicate the study on the male population too for gender differences. Future research may explore other factors including the moderating role of cultural background and diversity on the relationship between job autonomy and organizational citizenship behavior

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